

DISTENDER D2.2: Co-creation approach report I

D2.2: Co-creation approach report I
WP2, T2.2

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Glossary

Abbreviation	Meaning
AF	Project Application Form
CCS	Core case study
D 2.1	Deliverable 2.1 Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework
D 2.2	Deliverable 2.2 Co-creation approach report I
D 3.1	Deliverable 3.1 Designing a flexible methodology to co-produce socio-economic scenarios
DSS	Decision support system
FCS	Following case study
PMP	Project Management Plan
PP	Project Partner
SH	Stakeholder
SSP	Shared Socio-economic Pathways
WP	Work package

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1 Introduction

According to Project Application Form (AF), stakeholder engagement within DISTENDER will employ a ‘co-design-test-transfer’ approach that supports active stakeholder and societal engagement in the end-user needs analysis, co-designing explorative scenarios and normative integrated strategies, the iterative application and testing of the tools, data and knowledge within the DSS and the transfer of the DSS to broader stakeholder communities.

The co-design-test-transfer approach refers to participatory activities in WP8 developing a DSS (decision support system), which by stronger involvement of the follower case studies will be tested and transferred. However, participatory activities related to socio-economic scenarios development (WP3) and robust strategies outlined for climate change adaptation and mitigation (WP6) can also follow this approach to pass the know how to any future case study using the DISTENDER approach. Accordingly, such process assures the transfer phase of co-creation and spreading the messages of adaptation and mitigation to climate change issues in the studied areas of various scales and characteristics, reflected in the so-called core case studies (CCS 01 Austria (BMK), CCS 02 The NE of the Netherlands (HUAS), CCS 03 Dehesa and Montado (EURAF), CCS 04 Guimaraes (GUIMARAES), CCS 05 Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)).

This deliverable is a report on the current stage of the setup and application of the co-creation framework to co-develop socio-economic scenarios. Therefore, firstly it brings some related overviews of the two related and/or backgrounding deliverables of the DISTENDER project, D2.1 Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework and D3.1 Designing a flexible methodology to co-produce socio-economic scenarios. Secondly, the deliverable D2.2 Co-creation approach report I reports on the actual co-creation process, highlighting its structure and the process itself run until May 19th, 2023. We would like to note here that this report addresses the activities related to the first set of the DISTENDER workshops addressing production of socio-economic scenarios. Particularly, it focusses on the chain of the preparatory activities, that took place from January 2023, when various focused bilateral discussions with the CCSs intensively started until May 16th - 19th when two final preparatory webinars and a try-session for the workshop in CCS 03 Dehesa and Montado (EURAF) took place.

We would like to stress once again, that the D2.2 Co-creation approach report I respects the Gran Agreement (GA) (foreseeing the submission of D2.2. on May 31st, 2023), however, it would be better placed at the end of all processes and preparations completed. As it depends on the workflow in WP3, it covers the current processes completed.

1.1 Vocabulary

This section elucidates some of the key or often used words in this report to prevent misunderstandings and misconceptions as well as vague interpretations that may occur because of not having a common ground of understandings. There are two essential components that form a DISTENDER co-creation framework: a. overarching co-creation concept, and b. framework of stakeholder engagement. Both terms are explained below.

overarching co-creation concept - a concept compound of a sequence of interrelated activities involving the main participatory event, its pre-activities and post-activities. For more see Annex 1 and/or D2.1 Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework.

framework of stakeholder involvement – a structural way how to involve stakeholders, following two main blocks of activities: a. identification of stakeholders, and b. engagement of stakeholders. For more see Annex 1 and/or D2.1 Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework.

socio-economic scenarios - plausible representations of futures with respect to key social and economic drivers, such as technological development, economic growth, and migration. For more see D 3.1 Designing a flexible methodology to co-produce socio-economic scenarios.

1.2 Starting points of D2.1 and its implementation in D2.2

The D2.1 is about the DISTENDER co-creation framework and its manifestation, including conceptualisation of stakeholders. It summarises on some key and most often used terms in relation to collaborative processes, shows a model for stakeholder involvement, focusing on processes of their identification, mapping and actual engagement, and outlines co-creation approaches in relation to three key DISTENDER participatory driven activities: a. socio-economic scenarios, b. adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies, and c. the decision support system (DSS).

This section reflects on two essential drivers of DISTENDER co-creation concept that are directly related and engaged with in the processes of preparation of the workshops for socio-economic scenarios development:

- The DISTENDER overarching co-creation concept, which consists of three interrelated parts: a.) supportive events that take place before the participatory event itself and can cover various content-related and technical preparations, clarifications and the like; b.) main participatory events; and c.) the activities that follow after the participatory event, which can address various open questions related to the participatory activity and its results, and

- The DISTENDER framework for stakeholder involvement, which consists of three interrelated activities: a.) preparation, b.) communication and c.) implementation, i.e. involvement into a final participatory event.

The two drivers are mutually related and can often run in parallel, but also interconnected. As this report (D2.2) covers the current stage of the process, according to the co-creation plan timeline, it refers to the following segments of the used framework, as shown in Figure 1. Regarding stakeholder engagement it covers all steps of the stakeholders’ identification process (A-B) and two of five steps of the stakeholders’ engagement process (C-D). The third step (E) was implemented for CCS 03 Dehesa and Montado (EURAF), which according to the co-creation plan is the first CCS running the socio-economic scenarios workshop. Regarding the overarching co-creation concept, several activities referring to preparatory activities to support the event were taking place, from bilateral discussions to overall discussions participated by all CCSs and related WPs partners, resulted in two supportive webinars, prepared in coproduction of WP2 and WP3. Figure 1 shows a general scheme covering those activities, however, details on processes, methods applied, and activities taken are reported in section 2.

Figure 1: Adapted schemes of the DISTENDER framework for stakeholder involvement and the DISTENDER overarching co-creation concept originally presented in D2.1 regarding the actual implementational aspects showing an interconnected process of stakeholders’ identification and engagement and activities related to designing, preparing and implementing the workshop.

1.3 Review and summary of D3.1 and its relation to D2.2

Deliverable D3.1 is a complex document encompassing a) a description of the Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs) and the SSPs that are of relevance for the core case study areas, b) the methodology for co-producing the socio-economic scenarios in stakeholder workshops, as well as c) scenario quantification methodology. For D2.2, a) and

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b) are of special significance, the first one giving the background and rationale to workshop implementation, and the second one providing essential methodological guidelines for scenario co-production.

In its role of supporting preparatory activities and implementation of the co-production activities/stakeholder workshops, WP2 takes over the content and methodology proposed in D3.1. By way of example, in D3.1 the aims and steps of the stakeholder workshops are explained in a detailed manner, going as far as mentioning potential co-production techniques. Also featured are preliminary workshop agendas for on-site and on-line events.

Further important aspects are presented in the section on case study specific considerations. It is highlighted that whereas the overall methodology for workshop organisation and implementation is the same, there may be differences in its application that are due to e. g. (non)existence of SSPs for the case study area, on-site or on-line format, as well as sectors that need to be included in the scenarios. It is expected that the proposed methodology will make it possible to balance the concerns of consistency that enables comparison across case studies, and flexibility which is needed to account for specific case study characteristics.

1.4 Co-creation workshops

Co-creation is a collaborative approach that involves scientists and stakeholders in science-informed decision-making. This practice implies that, once specific decisions requiring scientific knowledge have been identified, scientists and stakeholders work together to define the scope and context of the problem, formulate research questions, select methods and analyse results. They also focus on making scientific inferences and developing strategies for the appropriate use of science in decision-making. The composition of stakeholders in a co-creation exercise can have a significant impact on the outcomes. The different perspectives, expertise, interests and personalities present in discussions can influence decisions and outcomes. However, iteration, i.e. the process of continuous review and feedback, can help mitigate some of these effects and promote constructive dialogue. It is essential that stakeholders have some incentive to participate in co-creation. They should have an expectation that their participation will lead to favourable outcomes. This implies that their contribution is recognised and valued, and that they are provided with clear information on how their input will be used in decision-making. Stakeholder participation is often motivated by their desire to understand their local environment, gain acceptance of decisions made, and understand the results of the evaluation.

One of the key challenges in transdisciplinary research, as is the case with the DISTENDER project in developing integrated climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies, is to understand the stakeholder environment. This involves identifying who the relevant stakeholders are and determining the population from which a representative sample can be drawn for participation in the co-creation process. It is necessary to consider the diversity of perspectives and experiences to ensure that all relevant viewpoints are taken into

account. To conduct effective co-creation workshops, it is important to select appropriate techniques. These techniques should specifically address the questions posed, be adapted to the time and resources available, and promote reflection and group experience. It is advisable to use simple and concrete tools that are easily understood and appropriate for all participants.

A co-creation workshop is an invaluable tool for engaging users in problem solving. In this type of workshop, facilitators prepare a structure or series of activities that allow users to understand a specific problem and then contribute their ideas and solutions to address it. In this context, users contribute their personal experience and point of view, which often leads to the generation of ideas and solutions that the project team, working in isolation, would not have considered. Importantly, the project team also benefits from co-creation workshops, as they gain a much deeper understanding of the problem by interacting and collaborating with users. Co-creation workshops are usually organised when the project team has clearly defined the problem to be addressed, but is willing to learn more about it and be open to new ideas and approaches. The team must be able to articulate the problem in a way that users participating in the workshop can understand and relate to.

Face-to-face workshops are a common way of conducting these activities, as they allow greater accessibility for users who do not have access to digital technology. In addition, physical collaboration on materials such as idea boards can be more fluid and tangible. However, there are situations where face-to-face workshops may be difficult or even impossible for some participants. In such cases, virtual workshops can be conducted online. However, it is essential to ensure that they are accessible to a wide range of participants and are not overwhelming, especially for those who are not used to virtual meetings. In addition, it is vital to ensure that the voices of those digitally excluded users continue to be heard. These groups may include people who have access to the internet but find it difficult to use unfamiliar technologies. To engage these users, creative message packs can be sent out with questions for them to answer and spaces for them to add their own ideas and suggestions. Instructions should be clear and simple, and participants can either complete the materials themselves and return them, or be interviewed by phone to share their ideas. Defining the roles of a workshop and each of its units is a fundamental aspect of ensuring the success and professionalism of the event. In remote sessions, this definition of roles becomes even more important, as multitasking can be more complicated to manage.

The content owner, who is responsible for sharing knowledge with the audience, establishing common ground and initiating the work. His/her role is critical to ensure that all participants have a solid understanding of the topic and can contribute effectively. The facilitator's role is to assist the content owner by controlling time, identifying those who wish to participate and encouraging them to share their ideas and comments. The facilitator's job is to help the content owner maintain focus and ensure that all voices are heard throughout the process. He/she ensures that the discussions flow logically and build on each other, i.e. he/she manages the issues. It is important to note that the facilitator should be neutral and should not become involved in the content of the discussions.

The role of content owner is often confused with that of facilitator, but there is a key difference between the two. While the moderator is responsible for the content, i.e. what is discussed in the workshop, such as agenda items, the facilitator is responsible for managing the process, i.e. how the issue in question is dealt with. In addition, he/she facilitates interaction between group members and encourages everyone to participate actively, thus managing the relationships within the workshop.

In additions, it is important to define other key roles in a workshop, such as the observer, the technical host and the note-takers. Each has a specific role that contributes to the smooth running of the workshop. The observer should be someone familiar with the workshop topics and be ready to intervene in case the moderator misses something important. The note taker is the person designated to document the workshop. He or she may take notes in real time on a shared board for all participants to access, or simply take notes for internal use and future reference. His role is to capture the key points, ideas and agreements reached during the workshop, which helps to maintain a clear and complete record of the discussions and decisions made.

The IT (technical host) person is another important member of the team, especially in remote workshops. His main role is to help participants with any technical problems that may arise during the event, such as explaining how to mute or activate the sound, share screens or log in to the platform used. Their goal is to ensure that all participants can make the most of the workshop experience without technical interruptions.

The presentation of the project is a crucial element at the beginning of the workshop, in DISTENDER is made by the coordinator (UPM). It is essential to give a clear idea about the purpose and potential of the project in order to involve and motivate the participants. By presenting the project and its objectives, you want people to understand its importance and feel inspired to contribute. In addition, by emphasizing the project's purpose and potential, you create an attractive vision that shows participants that their contribution will be valuable and useful.

DISTENDER workshops are events organized, recruited and convened by CCS partners, strictly following the ethics requirements and procedures defined in WP12 Ethics, in terms of data protection and participation of outsiders. Regarding the structure of the workshop team for developing DISTENDER local climate scenarios, it is suggested to have a lead facilitator who oversees the entire event. In addition, it is recommended to have four scenario facilitators, each responsible for a specific scenario. Likewise, four nota takers should be assigned, who will be responsible for properly recording and capturing all relevant information during the workshop. Each scenario team will work in breaking groups.

2 Report

This section refers to the process and steps achieved/ implemented in the preparatory phases of the workshops related to WP3 activities. Co-creative activities of this process were strongly depending on the stages of readiness of CCSs and the level of known details of proposed workshops (input of WP3).

Further, the subsections firstly comment on the detailed co-creation plan design, secondly the chapter reflects on the methods and tools applied in this process, and finally outlines some limitations recognised or identified along the process.

2.1 Co-creation plan and its timeline

According to the general co-creation plan, provided in D2.1, the first co-creation activity addressed participatory event Socio-economic scenario development. To get a concrete and well-structured co-creation plan for this particular event, the initial basic baseline provided in D2.1 (see Table 1) was firstly detailly shaped. Accordingly, a detailed action plan covering the T2.2 activities related to socio-economic scenarios development in line with the time span of T3.3 Co-development of socio-economic scenarios, was proposed.

Table 1: Section of the entire general co-creation plan (see D2.1), relevant for the first run of the participatory activities – workshops with stakeholders for socio-economic scenarios development.

WPs/ Tasks/ Subtasks	Co-creation activity title	Timeline	Main partners involved + tasks	Additional info
WP3, Task 3.3 + co-production of WP 2, WP6 and WP9	Participatory event 1 per case study: Scenario development	According to PMP	WUR, UIRS, SC, UoC, alongside KVC and case studies: BMK, HUAS, EURAF, GUIMARAES, CMT _o . <i>* tasks will be clearly stated in each process plan supporting the activity.</i>	Preceded by preparatory webinar; Optional follow-up discussions if needed

A complex excel file was set up and used as the means of developing and executing this plan. The document allows for dynamic process set up, its implementation and maintenance, and is commented in detail from its structure and operational point of view in section 2.2 and its sub-sections. Whereas is the general timeline with the main steps achieved in the process shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Timeline of T 2.2 Co-creation methods and activities showing the workflow and main steps achieved.

This process started with some informal bilateral meetings between WPs (WP2, WP3, WP9) and individual CCSs starting to uncover open issues and discussing optional solutions regarding various aims, from structure of the stakeholders needed, the issues of addressing them on optimal ways and times, to practical questions referring to agendas of the workshops, pros and cons regarding the manner the workshop may be held (live versus online), including language issues, such as holding a workshop in a native language or in English or discussing inner capacities of the CCS to support the workshop etc.. Based on such discussions some common issues were detected and then overall discussions were called so explanations or selected solutions were presented and debated among all CCSs and related WPs, such as WP3 or WP9.

For example, an overall meeting on Consultation with the stakeholders before the workshops was held on April 18th, 2023. When workshops scheduled come closer, two joint WP2-WP3 supportive training webinars were organised. All WP2 partners and other related DISTENDER partners were involved, i.e. CCSs, follower case studies (FCSs), WP3 partners that provide the content of the workshops, and all partners involved in facilitation of the workshops. The two webinars were scheduled one day after another, starting on May 16th, 2023, with the webinar on the content of the workshop, focussing on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), as the main subject of the coming workshop. The webinar on May 17th 2023 focused on technical and implementational issues of the workshop, reviewing the workshop process document with the focus on the different sections of the workshop, the roles of actors within each section, with a great emphasis also on how to facilitate, manage and shape the processes, including the exact methods used for various

activities foreseen (e.g. insights from T3.2 referring to designing a flexible methodology to co-produce socio-economic scenarios). For the workshops that decided to be run in an online environment, also online environment of the MS Teams, tools and their implementation and use were demonstrated.

2.2 Methods and tools of co-creation approach

This section focusses on methods and tools to enable and support smooth and efficient communication as well as progress of content related materials on time for all involved. Co-creation is a process, it is a dynamic state where different actors get involved at different levels with (may be) different expectations. Therefore, it was of key importance to provide a platform for communication and information exchange but also for assignment of tasks and deadlines for the activities recognised.

According to PMP there are several tasks that either bring insights to activities of T 2.2 (co-creation methods and activities) or require close simultaneous collaboration running at the same time (T3.2 with a focus on methodology to co-develop socio-economic scenario, T3.3 with a focus on co-development of socio-economic scenarios, T9.1 with a focus on participation to co-develop socio-economic scenarios). Therefore, the first practical move was a creation of a joint folder at the DISTENDER sharepoint. An operative common excel table was then set up, becoming a live template document for preparation, implementation and monitoring activities of participatory events. This document is understood as a dynamic process set-up template document and will serve as a virtual home for all participatory activities planned within the DISTENDER project. Its structure and operational concept are presented in section 2.2.1.

Stakeholder involvement process followed the proposed scheme (see left side of Figure 1, or Annex 1): stakeholder identification closely followed the structure of the stakeholders required by WP3. In the stakeholder engagement stage CCSs (as hosts of the workshops) were individually given a support advice with and emphasis as to how to communicate to attract as many stakeholders as possible/needed, and were offered a guide for invitation preparations to be able to fulfil the expected number of participants.

Detailed course of the process followed the Dynamic process set-up approach, which steps and/or loops are commented in separate sections below.

2.2.1 Dynamic process set-up

This section is about the excel template document, as a virtual home for all participatory activities of DISTENDER project. It firstly comments the structure of the template and shows some of its segments to address its practicality and operational ability in support of the co-creation processes.

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There are five general sections suggested, addressing specific topics entitled as follows: a.) general, b.) CCS related issues, c.) pre-participatory event activities, d.) participatory event, and e.) post-participatory event activities. According to this overall division, sheets in the excel table were created to correspond with different topics within the proposed divisions.

- a.) **General** is addressed via two sheets of the excel template document:
- *Sheet 1: General info* that involves information about the date of the workshop, format of the workshop, language used at the workshop and the date of the first invitation (announcement) for each CCS to keep key information at one hand.
 - *Sheet 2: Gant* which serves as a calendar and a visual representation of the activities organised for each CCS or a group of them.
- b.) **CCS related issues** is addressed via two sheets of the excel template document:
- *Sheet 1: CCS doubts*, where CCSs via WP9 representative could express any concerns or questions that may be relevant for the workshop preparation or process, so the project partners being involved into workshop preparation and implementation can address them promptly.
 - *Sheet 2: Technical information from CCS*, where results from a short in-WP2 survey about the roles of various implementors needed to conduct the workshop were explained and CCS familiarity with such roles and their in-house capacities for playing these roles at the workshops were checked.
- c.) **Pre-participatory event activities** are addressed via two sheets of the excel template document:
- *Sheet 1: Pre-workshop* is a very detailly structured section addressing tasks outlined, their character and characteristics, responsible project partner for implementing the task, specifying subtasks if needed and responsible partners accordingly. Coloured marks for “done/in progress” were applied, too.
 - *Sheet 2: Agenda* was created solely for updating workshop agendas, as it represents the backbone of all the activities.
- d.) **Participatory event** addresses actual implementation of the workshop and is composed by:
- *Sheet 1: Workshop*. As none of the workshops has been implemented and completed with the reports on workshop yet (by the deadline for submission of D2.2), there are no specific tasks or activities commented as they happened at the workshop. However, essential information on the roles taken are provided, such as main facilitator, co-facilitator, note-taker, observer, DISTENDER presenter, host, follower attending etc.
- e.) **Post participatory event** addresses any issues relevant after the workshop and is composed by:
- *Sheet 1: Post-workshop*. It has not been developed in detail yet as also the workshops implementation may open up some insights to be noted. However,

remarks about some materials to be prepared and activities taken are marked, e.g. follow up for stakeholders, information transition to all DISTENDER partners, feedback session for other workshops, minutes, post-workshop survey.

Figure 3: An example of the excel template document opened at *Sheet 1: General info* at the early stage of the workshop development process.

2.2.1.1 Pre-workshop activities

There were 28 tasks listed and organised to be realised before the workshop itself. Some of them were divided into subtask. Each task was then commented against the following aspects: a.) category of task (e.g. content, technical, stakeholder engagement), b.) responsible PP for carrying out the task or organise the appropriate group of PPs to join forces, c.) specifying sub-task in terms of what to do? (e.g. finalise the agenda, communicate the CCS, outline the CCS specific materials, organise translation etc., d.) responsible PP for the subtask, e.) deadline of the (sub) task, and f.) result (e.g. completed, in progress). Figure 4 illustrates one moment in time in this process.

Having all the activities and related information listed, main responsible PPs for each workshop planned were appointed, as shown in Table 2.

Figure 4: An example of the excel template document opened at Sheet 1: Pre-workshop.

Table 2: A basic overall information about the workshops

	Austria (BMK)	North-east of The Netherlands (HUAS)	Dehesas and Montados (EURAF)	Guimarães (GIMARAES)	The Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)
Date of the WP3 workshop	26. 5. 2023	6.6.2023	22., 23. 5.2023	29. - 30. 6. 2023	7. - 8. 6. 2023
type	live	live	online	online	online
Main responsible PP for workshop implementation	WUR	WUR	KVC	KVC	UIRS
Supportive responsible PP for workshop implementation	UNI GRAZ	WUR	UPM	KVC	UIRS
External costs related to workshops paid by	UIRS	WUR	KVC	SC	UIRS

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Any material was prepared so, that the general document, as much as possible common document that can be applicable for every CCS, was prepared and then it was modified according to specifics of each CCS. Thus, for example, WP3 prepared general process documents of the workshop covering the required contents, typology of preferred methods for live or online event, and then appointed responsible partners with support of WP3 (content-wise) and WP2 (technical and process-wise) and in close contact with CCS hosting the workshop finalised the materials. Figure 5 shows an example of the general agenda of a two-days online workshop taking place in the morning. Each section on the agenda was then further detailed and description of the activities and roles taken by implementers were described.

Day 1 – 3 hours

Timeslot	Duration	Agenda item	
CET 9:45-10:00	15 min	Open virtual room, check registration	1. PART
CET 10:00-10:15	15 min	Welcome and overall introduction	
CET 10:15-10:20	5 min	Who is who	
CET 10:20-10:40	20 min	Participant introductions (plenary)	
CET 10:40-10:55	15 min	Introducing the SSPs	
CET 10:55-11:25	30 min	Plenary on main factors (building blocks for scenarios, based on survey)	
CET 11:30-11:35	5 min	Break or energizer	2. PART
CET 11:25-11:30	5 min	Group divisions	
CET 11:35-12:55	1 hr 20 min	BOG1: developing the SSP narratives	
CET 12:55-13:00	5 min	Wrap-up (invite them to come tomorrow again, emphasize continual process)	

Day 2 – 3 hours

Timeslot	Duration	Agenda item	
CET 9:45-10:00	15 min	Open virtual room, check registration	3. PART
CET 10:00-11:00	60 min	Plenary: presentations on SSPs (15 min/group, including discussion)	
CET 11:00-11:50	50 min	BOG2: trend indications (& land use change)	
CET 11:50-11:55	5 min	Break or energizer	4. PART
CET 11:55-12:45	50 min	BOG3: current climate change strategies (note: starts in plenary)	
CET 12:45-13:00	15 min	Next steps and closing statements	

Figure 5: Example of a product of the task “finalisation of the general agenda”.

Figure 5 outlines a final general structure of the workshop showing that there are four general sections, where parts 2 to 4 requires group work.

2.2.2 Stakeholder engagement

Stakeholders for the workshop on socio-economic scenarios were selected on the basis of the Prospex-CQI method (Gramberger et al., 2015; D2.1, D3.1). The CCSs were handed in predesigned excel tables with the proposed topical categories such as a.) institutional affiliation spanning from government, science, NGO, art, business, citizen; b.) sectoral affiliation spanning from water, energy, soil/spatial planning, agriculture/forestry/soil to health; and demographic categories such as a.) age, b.) gender, and c.) vulnerable groups.

CCSs were following the proposed table and were mapping possible stakeholders and making priority lists to contact them to get final selections for the workshops. They were advised by the WP3 regarding the structure of the stakeholders and by WP2 regarding the further steps on communication. The goal was to involve 20-25 active stakeholders for each CCS workshop. The team has also been prepared for the cases if the actual number of participants would be smaller. In such case the relisting and regrouping procedures were prepared so that priority of SSP preparations would be kept as well as the most various representation of SHs would be present in the groups of SHs that would prepare the SSPs. Having the shortlists ready, also DISTENDER communication and stakeholder engagement rules were followed.

2.3 Limitations

Co-creation is indeed a process, which is quite structured. It foresees great division of roles but heading for a common goal. What matters is a good atmosphere and comfortable feelings of those involved. Inhibition of free and relaxed communication among all participants may be an important obstacle. Incompetent interference in the process can stifle creativity. Particularly in the preparation phase, untimely access to information is also a constraint.

3 Conclusion and further steps

Process wise, D2.2 covers in detail the preparatory stages of co-creative process in the current stage of the process. The concept and steps were set up. Experiences gained. The dynamic SHP placed excel file template was of great help to communicate and fill in the knowledge or info available. Some limitations can be also overcome on the basis of these experiences.

Based on the experiences of the preparatory stages of co-creative activities and the fact that the third part of workshop on socio economic scenarios brings insights for strategies-related issues (see Figure 5), we aim that the D2.3 Co-creation report II, which will cover the report on the co-creation process addressing adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies (WP6) will cover the participatory event section of the DISTENDER overarching co-creation concept (actual workshop process).

4 References

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1. Annex1: DISTENDER overarching co-creation concept & DISTENDER framework for stakeholder involvement (for more see D2.1)

DISTENDER Overarching co-creation concept

There are three compounds of activities:

- main participatory events,
- supportive events that take place before the participatory event itself and can cover various technical preparations, clarifications and the like, and
- the activities that follow after the participatory event, which can address various open questions related to the participatory activity and its results.

According to DISTENDER project, WPs that built greatly on the participation activities are WP3, WP6 and WP8, therefore a schematic diagram upon the general scheme illustrates how the co-creation concept is reflected in these particular WPs, showing also who is expected to be involved in any of the phases (before, at, after) of co-creation, and points out as well, that the system is open for inclusion of any other partner or expert needed.

<i>when?</i>	before	at	after
<i>what?</i> <i>what kind?</i>			
<i>who?</i>	<p>WP2 + WP3 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP2 + WP6 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP2 + WP8 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p>	<p>WP3 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP6 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP8 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p>	<p>WP3 + WP2 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP6 + WP2 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP8 + WP2 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p>

Schematic diagram showing DISTENDER overarching co-creation concept.

DISTENDER framework for stakeholder involvement

In principle, the DISTENDER framework for stakeholder identification and engagement reflects three main slots of activities:

- preparation,
- communication and
- implementation

They can be detailed as follows:

- Identification of general topic upon which the stakeholders are going to be addressed, and related initial identification of possible stakeholders,
- Identification of specific question(s) that are the basis for each specific participatory activity,
- Set up criteria for wanted structure and shares of stakeholders to address the specific topic of the participatory activity as best as possible,
- Creation and finalisation of list of stakeholders requested for a specific participatory activity,
- Selection of the ways and media of communication with stakeholders,
- Early focused communication with stakeholders significant for the basic information about the planned event and about its expected term,
- Final invitation with the information providing the brief but exact information about WHAT, WHERE, WHEN, WHY, and HOW,
- Actual implementation of the participatory activity following the well-prepared process plan,
- After participatory communication activities.

Schematic diagram showing DISTENDER framework for stakeholder involvement.

